

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR IMPORT SUBSTITUTION IN THE AVIATION INDUSTRY

Tikhonov A.I.

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor, Head of Department No. 512, Moscow Aviation Institute (National Research University), Moscow, Russia

Prosvirina N.V.

Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor, Associate Professor of Department No. 512, Moscow Aviation Institute (National Research University), Moscow, Russia

Abstract

At present, the import substitution policy in the Russian aviation industry remains partially implemented. Many of its aspects are either in the early stages of implementation or are still in the planning phase. This is due to the lack of effective import substitution mechanisms in key sectors of the Russian economy, hindering the achievement of the set goals within this policy framework. The research theme focuses on developing a methodological approach to the formation of an organizational-economic mechanism for import substitution in the aviation industry amid increasing demands for economic and information security. The study aims to address the challenges associated with the current state of import substitution policies and proposes strategies for the effective integration of these mechanisms into the aviation sector.

Keywords: aviation industry, import substitution, import independence, competitiveness, aircraft, organizational-economic mechanism.

The aviation industry is a key sector of the global market. Currently, only five countries worldwide engage in full-scale production of aviation technology. For Russia, the aviation industry is a priority sector that can provide domestic economy with leadership and high competitiveness in the global market. The main vector of development for the aviation industry at present is import substitution, as the external conditions in which the aviation industry operates pose a threat to the economic security of the Russian Federation. Currently, import substitution policy in Russia is being successfully implemented. However, the strong dependence on imports in mechanical engineering remains very high, necessitating the development of a more effective import substitution mechanism for the aviation industry.

The organizational component of the organizational-economic mechanism for import substitution in the aviation industry is primarily related to the reserves of import substitution. These represent the existing opportunities for enterprises to increase their efficiency by replacing imported goods, participating in the creation of the final product, or competing with it. The implementation of these opportunities is accompanied by a reduction in the dependence of the enterprise on imports. Based on the proposed definition, two types of sources of import substitution can be identified:

1. Establishing import-substituting production.
2. Replacing imported components with domestic counterparts.

The proposed interpretation emphasizes that the successful implementation of import substitution projects at the micro level not only contributes to the increased efficiency of the enterprise itself but also, in

perspective, leads to an acceleration of the overall aviation industry's growth by reducing the import dependence of the Russian economy.

To implement the proposed import substitution mechanism, it is suggested to categorize all available reserves into two groups:

- 1) External Reserves;
- 2) Internal Reserves.

The proposed structure of external reserves for import substitution in the aerospace enterprise:

– National Reserves – utilization of reserves based on the country's characteristics (raw materials, national, tax-related, etc.).

– Industry-specific Reserves – utilization of reserves based on the characteristics of the aviation industry.

– Regional Reserves – reserves specific to a certain region.

– Personnel Reserves – the presence of universities and other educational institutions preparing professionals with the required specialties for the enterprise.

The specificity of external reserves lies in the fact that they are created without the influence of a specific enterprise. The task of the aerospace industry enterprise is to make proper use of these reserves within the framework of the organizational and economic mechanism of import substitution. The effectiveness of utilizing external reserves can be measured by the level of competitiveness of the aviation industry's products compared to imported counterparts.

In contrast to external reserves, internal reserves result from the utilization of specific enterprise capabilities. The proposed structure of internal reserves for import substitution in the aerospace enterprise:

- Reserves for increasing the efficiency of the production process;
- Reserves for improving the quality of aviation products;
- Marketing reserves;
- Management personnel reserves.

Reserves can also be classified as follows:

1) Reserves for substituting imports used in the production process of the aerospace industry's products.

2) Reserves for substituting imported production of aerospace industry products.

Depending on the category to which the identified reserves belong, methods of implementation are selected for them, evaluation criteria are determined, and factors influencing them are identified. The process of forming reserves for import substitution in the aerospace industry is also influenced by certain factors, with the most significant ones presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Key Factors Influencing the Application of Import Substitution Reserves in the Aviation Industry

The determination of the current level of internal reserves is proposed to be carried out within the framework of assessing import substitution potential (Formula 1) [1], [2].

$$PT_{imp} = V_{potential} / V_{imp}, \quad (1)$$

Where PT_{imp} is the import substitution potential at the aircraft manufacturing enterprise;

$V_{potential}$ is the volume of imports that can be replaced by domestic production;

V_{imp} is the total volume of imports.

The economic component of the proposed import substitution mechanism is associated with evaluating the effectiveness of import substitution projects at all levels. This is crucial because an important step in assessing import substitution policy in the aviation industry is evaluating its effectiveness. Emphasis should be placed on the multidimensionality of such an assessment, as the relevant results require consideration of the levels presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Levels of Assessment of Import Substitution Policy Effectiveness in the Aviation Industry

The division of effectiveness assessment into three levels is justified by the fact that each of the identified levels requires a different approach to assessing the innovation potential of the aviation industry. Thus, emphasis should be placed on:

1. Macro-level management of the industrial innovation potential of the sector;
2. Meso-level management of innovation-industrial clusters in the aviation industry;
3. Enterprise-level management of the innovation potential of aviation industry enterprises.

In addition, specific problems are identified at different levels. At the micro-level, the key indicator is the competitiveness of the enterprise, which is directly influenced by the frequency and quality of innovations implemented, including those within the framework of import-substituted goods. At the meso-level, the ultimate indicator is the growth rate of regional aviation industry (its condition: dynamic growth or stagnation), significantly affected by the share of innovations in import-substituted productions. At the macro-level, the indicators are the competitiveness of the industry as a

whole and the level of national economic security, influenced by the level of innovation activity in import-substituted productions.

Within the scope of the scientific research, emphasis was placed on assessing the effectiveness of import substitution projects at the micro-level, as this level lacks an adapted methodology for modern challenges. The author's position is that the assessment of the effectiveness of implementing import substitution policy in the aviation industry at the micro-level is based on a systemic approach, which involves considering a set of multi-criteria indicators, each of which demonstrates the potential economic impact on all significant aspects of the import substitution process. In this regard, a system of indicators was developed, reflecting the effectiveness of implementing import substitution policy in the aviation industry at all levels. The advantage of the indicator system is its completeness in terms of the breadth of coverage of import substitution policy aspects, as well as freedom from distorting factors, due to the presence of cost indicators (Table 1).

Table 1.

Indicator System for Assessing the Effectiveness of Import Substitution Policy Implementation in the Aviation Industry at All Levels

Indicator Name	Guidelines
Micro-level	
Natural production import dependency coefficient	The proportion of import component names (types of raw materials) necessary for the production of aviation industry goods in the total number of component names (types of raw materials)
Value-based production import dependency coefficient	The ratio of the total cost of imported components (types of raw materials) required for the production of aviation industry goods to the overall cost of all components (types of raw materials) forming the calculated cost of the product
Actual natural import coverage coefficient	The ratio of the quantity of domestic components (types of raw materials and materials) used in the production of aviation industry goods to the quantity of imported components (types of raw materials and materials)
Actual value-based import coverage coefficient	The ratio of the cost of domestic components (types of raw materials and materials) used in the production of aviation industry goods to the cost of imported components (types of raw materials and materials)
Potential natural import coverage coefficient	The ratio of the quantity of domestic components (types of raw materials and materials) that can be replaced in the production of aviation industry goods to the quantity of imported components (types of raw materials and materials).
Potential value-based import coverage coefficient	The ratio of the cost of domestic components (types of raw materials and materials) that can be replaced in the production of aviation industry goods to the cost of imported components (types of raw materials and materials)
Natural import substitution coefficient	The ratio of the quantity of domestic components (types of raw materials and materials) used in the production of aviation industry goods to the total quantity of components (types of raw materials and materials)
Value-based import substitution coefficient	The ratio of the cost of domestic components (types of raw materials and materials) used in the production of aviation industry goods to the cost of the total quantity of components (types of raw materials and materials)
Mesolevel and macrolevel	
Import burden coefficient	Ratio of the volume of aviation industry goods imports to the regional gross product or gross industry product.
Import priority coefficient	Ratio of the growth rates of aviation industry goods imports and exports
Import substitution coefficient	Ratio of the cost of domestic resources (material-technical, financial, informational, etc.) used for the production of aviation industry goods to the total cost of resources
Price superiority coefficient of foreign trade	Ratio of export and import prices for aviation industry goods

In the course of the current research, it is necessary to validate the effectiveness indicator system at the micro-level. To do this, we will select data from the key enterprise in the aviation industry, PJSC "United Aircraft Corporation" (UAC) [3], [4]. The use of the developed toolkit for assessing the effectiveness of import

substitution policy implementation in the aviation industry requires the determination of certain assumptions. For testing the indicator system, let's assume that the calculation is based on 100 units of high-tech products, namely: component products. The initial data for the assessment is presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

List of Initial Data for Evaluating the Effectiveness of Import Substitution Policy in the Aviation Industry

No.	Element	Cost of Element, '000 RUB	Procurement Source
1	Epoxy Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic	650	Import
2	Aluminum Alloy	265,2	Domestic Production
3	Epoxy Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastic	320	Import
4	Titanium Alloy	170	Domestic Production
5	Steel Angles	230	Import
6	Bolts	43,2	Import
7	Nuts	10,6	Import
8	Rivets	1,4	Domestic Production
9	Adhesive	32	Import
10	Varnish	34	Import
11	Hinges	532	Domestic Production
12	Fabric Bearings for Hinge Joints	110	Import
13	Bushings	44	Import
14	Polyurethane Foam	218	Import
15	Spring-hydraulic Dampers	18	Domestic Production
16	Cardboard Boxes	124	Domestic Production
17	Detachable Connection	68	Import
	Percentage of Import in Natural Form		62,6 %
	Percentage of Import in Value Form		60,4 %
	Total	2870,4	

The evaluation methodology using the proposed system enables decision-making regarding the effectiveness of import substitution projects for specific enterprises, aimed at reducing the dependency of aviation industry enterprises on imported goods. At the outset of the analysis, the enterprise's dependency on imports was:

- In physical terms – 62.6%;
- In monetary terms – 60.4%.

These figures demonstrate a high level of import dependency for the enterprise, indicating the necessity

to develop projects for importing substitutes for components in the manufacturing process of the products. Table 3 presents the calculated actual and potential values of the import coverage and import substitution coefficients. The comparison of the coefficients provided in Table 2 showcases the high effectiveness of this project, as its implementation will significantly decrease the enterprise's degree of import dependency. Consequently, at the micro-level, the import substitution policy in the aviation industry is being implemented at a low level.

Table 3.

Comparative analysis of actual and potential efficiency coefficients.

Coefficients	Estimated (actual)	Potential (as a result of project implementation)	Change, +,-
1. Import Coverage Coefficients			
1.1. Natural Import Coverage Coefficient	1,94	0,46	-1,48
1.2. Value-based Import Coverage Coefficient	1,8	0,21	-1,59
2. Import Substitution Coefficients			
2.1. Natural Import Substitution Coefficient	62,6	55,4	7,2
2.2. Value-based Import Substitution Coefficient	60,4	41,7	18,7

The aviation industry enterprises exhibit a high degree of import dependence, necessitating the development of an efficient import substitution mechanism. This includes a methodological approach to the development of the organizational-economic framework for

import substitution in the context of heightened requirements for the economic and information security of the aviation industry.

Therefore, it is imperative to substantiate the effectiveness of the import substitution strategy in the aviation industry using the proposed methods and methodological approach.

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